

The factors that influence protostellar multiplicity

I. Gas temperature, density, and mass in Perseus with Nobeyama

N. M. Murillo^{1,2}, C. M. Fuchs³, D. Harsono⁴, N. Sakai¹, A. Hacar⁵, D. Johnstone^{6,7}, R. Mignon-Risse^{8,9}, S. Zeng¹,
T.-H. Hsieh¹⁰, Y.-L. Yang¹, J. J. Tobin¹¹ and M. V. Persson¹²

¹ Star and Planet Formation Laboratory, RIKEN Cluster for Pioneering Research, Wako, Saitama 351-0198, Japan
e-mail: nmurillo@astro.unam.mx

² Instituto de Astronomía, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, AP106, Ensenada CP 22830, B. C., México

³ Fox2Space - FTSCO, The Fault Tolerant Satellite Computer Organization, Weingunzstrasse 4, 4040 Linz, Austria

⁴ Institute of Astronomy, Department of Physics, National Tsing Hua University, Hsinchu, Taiwan

⁵ Department of Astrophysics, University of Vienna, Türkenschanzstrasse 17, A-1180 Vienna

⁶ NRC Herzberg Astronomy and Astrophysics, 5071 West Saanich Rd, Victoria, BC, V9E 2E7, Canada

⁷ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, V8P 5C2, Canada

⁸ Institutt for Fysikk, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Høgskoleringen 5, Trondheim, 7491, Norway

⁹ Université Paris Cité CNRS, CNES, Astroparticule et Cosmologie, F-75013 Paris, France

¹⁰ Max-Planck-Institut für extraterrestrische Physik, Giessenbachstrasse 1, D-85748 Garching, Germany

¹¹ National Radio Astronomy Observatory, Charlottesville, VA 22903, USA

¹² Independent researcher, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Context. Protostellar multiplicity is common at all stages and mass ranges. However, the factors that determine the multiplicity of protostellar systems have not been systematically characterized through their molecular gas.

Aims. This work seeks to characterize the physical properties of the Perseus Molecular Cloud at ≥ 5000 AU scales through mapping of diagnostic molecular lines.

Methods. Nobeyama 45m Radio Observatory (NRO) on-the-fly maps of HCN, HNC, HCO⁺, and N₂H⁺ ($J = 1-0$) toward five sub-regions in Perseus, complemented with single pointing Atacama Pathfinder EXperiment (APEX) observations of HNC ($J = 4-3$) are used to derive physical parameters of the dense gas. Both observations have spatial resolutions of $\sim 18''$, equivalent to ~ 5000 AU scales at the distance of Perseus. Kinetic gas temperature is derived from the $I(\text{HCN})/I(\text{HNC})$ J ratio, and H₂ density is obtained from the HNC $J=4-3/J=1-0$ ratio. These parameters are used to obtain the N₂H⁺ (cold) and HCO⁺ (warm) gas masses. The inferred and derived parameters are then compared to source parameters, including protostellar multiplicity, bolometric luminosity and dust envelope mass.

Results. Inferred mean kinetic gas temperature ($I(\text{HCN})/I(\text{HNC})$ $J=1-0$ ratio; ranging between 15 and 26 K), and H₂ volumetric density (HNC $J=4-3/J=1-0$; $10^5 - 10^6$ cm⁻³) do not show correlations with multiplicity in Perseus. The derived gas and dust masses, 1.3 to 16×10^{-9} M_⊙ for the cold gas mass (N₂H⁺), 0.1 to 25 M_⊙ for envelope dust masses ($850 \mu\text{m}$), and 0.8 to 10×10^{-10} M_⊙ for the warm gas mass (HCO⁺), are correlated to multiplicity and number of protostellar components. The warm gas masses are a factor of 16 lower than the cold gas masses.

Conclusions. This work shows that gas and dust mass is correlated to multiplicity at ~ 5000 AU scales in Perseus. Higher order multiples tend to have higher gas and dust masses in general, while close binaries (separations $\leq 7''$) and single protostars have similar gas and dust mass distributions. On the other hand, H₂ density and kinetic gas temperature do not show any correlation with multiplicity.

Key words. astrochemistry - stars: formation - stars: low-mass - ISM: molecules - methods: observational - methods: statistical

Appendix A: Observational data

The parameters for the protostellar systems and starless cores are listed in Tables A.1 and A.2, respectively. Transitions, frequencies, upper energy levels E_{up} and Einstein coefficients A_{ij} for the molecular species presented in this work are listed in Table A.3. Gas kinetic temperature derived from the HCN/HNC ratio (see map in Fig. B.7) are given in Table A.4. The listed values are the mean value within a region of $18''$ diameter centered on the positions given in Table A.1. Table A.4 also lists the dust temperature from Zari et al. (2016) and NH_3 kinetic temperature from Friesen et al. (2017) for the same positions and region size. The derived H_2 densities, N_2H^+ and HCO^+ column densities and gas masses, together with the dust envelope masses derived from the $850\ \mu\text{m}$ continuum maps (Arce et al. 2010) are listed in Table A.5. The data from these tables is used to plot Figures 2 and 3.

Appendix B: Intensity integrated maps

Intensity integrated maps were produced using the `bettermoments` python library (Teague & Foreman-Mackey 2018; Teague 2019). Before generating the intensity integrated maps, the image edges (xy) were cut off in order to reduce noisy pixels which did not contribute significant data. The noise level of the maps was calculated using the `bettermoments` routine `estimate_rms` and using 40 channels on either end of the data cube for HCN, N_2H^+ and ^{13}CO , and 100 channels for HCO^+ , HNC and C^{18}O . The choice of channels was based on the presence of hyperfine components and line width. Due to the complexity of the NGC1333 map, `estimate_rms` did not provide a reasonable estimate for the combined maps of HCO^+ and HNC. Thus the noise level was estimated from the individual maps instead of the combined map, resulting in noise levels of 0.98 and 0.82 K for HCO^+ and HNC, respectively. The noise level for the other regions using the above method was in good agreement with the `estimate_rms` value. A channel mask was then applied to the data cube to select channels with relevant line emission. The channel range for N_2H^+ and HCN includes all hyperfine components. Values above 40 K and below -5 K were clipped using `get_threshold_mask` to avoid any pixels that would generate artifacts. The upper limit was based from the CO isotopologue maps, which present the brightest emission. The intensity integrated maps were then generated with `collapse_zeroth`. Finally, the maps were clipped to 3σ or 5σ depending on the integrated intensity peak and are termed the clipped integrated intensity maps in this work (e.g., Section 5.2). The σ value was taken from the uncertainty map generated by `bettermoments`. The resulting maps are shown in Figures B.1 to B.6. Here a brief description of each map is given.

Hydrogen cyanide (HCN 1–0, Fig. B.1) is present in all surveyed regions and shows a clumpy distribution. The HCN emission is brightest in NGC1333 and L1448 with peaks toward NGC1333 IRAS4A ($28\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$) and L1448 N ($19\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$). Bright HCN peaks ($\sim 30\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$) are observed west of NGC1333 IRAS2A and south of NGC1333 IRAS4A, most likely arising from their respective outflow cavities. The regions IC348, B1, L1455 and IRAS03282 have weaker emission than NGC1333, with peak integrated intensities of 12, 14, 7, 7 K km s^{-1} , respectively. The isolated systems, Per25 and IRAS03292 show the weakest integrated intensities peaking at <2 and $3\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$, respectively.

Formyl cation (HCO^+ 1–0, Fig. B.2) is detected in all regions. Its emission is brightest in NGC1333, with the strongest emission located around the SVS13 system (peak: $17\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$)

and IRAS6 (peak: $22\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$). The HCO^+ emission is weaker toward L1448 (peak: $10\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$), L1455 (peak: $11\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$) and IC348 (peak: $9\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$). In L1448 and L1455 the integrated intensity is similar toward all sources, while in IC348 the emission peaks around Per 32 (but not ED366) and the starless cores in the west. Surprisingly, B1 is not bright in HCO^+ with integrated intensities $<5\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$, despite presence of young protostars (B1-bN and B1-bS) and active star formation. IRAS03282 presents HCO^+ emission peaking at $3\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ and extending north to south. The other two isolated systems, Per25 and IRAS03292, present weak and compact HCO^+ emission with intensities $<2\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$.

Hydrogen isocyanide (HNC 1–0, Fig. B.3) is detected in all regions and toward all sources. The spatial distribution of both isomers, HNC and HCN, is similar, but HNC shows a less clumpy and more smooth morphology than HCN. NGC1333 and L1448 are equally bright, with the peak integrated intensity of $15\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ located around both NGC1333 SVS13 and L1448 N. IC348, B1, L1455 and IRAS03282 have similar integrated intensities (8, 8, 7, 6 K km s^{-1} respectively). IRAS03292 presents emission peaking at $3\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$, with the bulk of the emission located to the southwest of the close binary. Per25 has weak HNC emission with integrated intensity $<2\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$.

Diazenylium (N_2H^+ 1–0, Fig. B.4) is present in all observed regions. Similar to HCN, HCO^+ and HNC, the brightest N_2H^+ emission is detected toward NGC1333 and L1448. In NGC1333 the emission is located between SVS13 and RNO 15 FIR peaking at $30\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. In L1448, the N_2H^+ peak is located near L1448 N B and peaks at $25\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. In B1, the peak emission (below $15\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$) is located on the system B1-b, with the rest of the region showing emission around $10\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. IRAS03292 and IRAS03282 show integrated intensities similar to B1, peaking at $10\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. IC348 and L1455 presents N_2H^+ emission peaking at $8\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$, while Per25 has much weaker emission peaking on-source at $5\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$.

Two carbon monoxide isotopologues, C^{18}O 1–0 (Fig. B.5) and ^{13}CO 1–0 (Fig. B.6), were observed and detected in all regions. The brightest C^{18}O emission is found toward B1, peaking at $9\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. Toward NGC1333 C^{18}O peaks at $8\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ and the bulk of the emission is located in an elongated structure stretching from IRAS7, SVS13 and IRAS2. An area of bright emission is detected around the starless core north of IRAS6. In L1448, the peak of C^{18}O is located near L1448 N-C with an integrated intensity peak of $6\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. No peak of C^{18}O is detected toward any of the sources in IC348. The maximum integrated intensity is $6\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. Similarly, L1455, IRAS03282 and IRAS03292 do not show on-source C^{18}O peaks, with maximum integrated intensity of $3\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ in the diffuse emission around the protostars. The C^{18}O emission toward Per25 is located on-source and extended around the source, peaking at $1\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. ^{13}CO emission is brightest in NGC1333 along the elongated structure observed in C^{18}O , peaking at $49\ \text{K km}^{-1}$ northeast of IRAS7. A similar peak is detected around the starless core north of IRAS6, consistent with the C^{18}O . IC348 and B1 present bright emission peaking at $30\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ on and around the sources, while L1455 peaks $25\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$ away from the sources. In L1448, the bulk of the C^{18}O is located around L1448 N, peaking at $26\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$. Both IRAS03292 and IRAS03282 peak at $10\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$, while Per25 peaks at $5\ \text{K km s}^{-1}$.

Both CO isotopologues show different structures to those traced by the other molecular species (HCN, HNC, HCO^+ or N_2H^+), and do not show a particular distribution relative to protostellar multiplicity (Fig. B.5 and B.6). This demonstrates

that CO is not the best tracer to examine the physical factors that influence star formation and evolution. The strongest ^{13}CO emission is found in NGC1333 extending northeast to southwest, passing along the IRAS7, SVS13 and IRAS2 cores. On the other hand, the brightest C^{18}O emission is observed toward the main part of B1, but not IRAS03292 and IRAS03282. The observed effects could be due to the optical depth of the ^{13}CO emission. The strong C^{18}O emission in B1 could be caused by higher masses in the region. However, we note that the N_2H^+ and HCO^+ gas masses in B1 are above the average, but are not the highest for all the sources surveyed in the Perseus molecular cloud. Hence the strong C^{18}O emission in B1 could be product of a chemical effect as well.

Appendix C: Additional statistics plots

Plot of all gas and dust masses that show significant correlations in the four classification schemes described in Section 5.5 are shown in Figure C.1. In addition, the correlations between masses and number of components are also shown. Classification scheme 4 (third column in Fig. C.1) visually shows a correlation between mass and number of components, albeit flatter than in the other classification schemes. However, the Pearson r and Spearman ρ do not reflect a statistically significant correlation.

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Fig. B.1. Integrated intensity maps of hydrogen cyanide HCN 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to the signal-to-noise ratio indicated next to the panel title (i.e., 5σ or 3σ). Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Table A.1. Sample of protostellar systems

System	Sources	RA	Dec	Projected Separation (")	Clustered? ^a	L_{bol} ($L_{\odot}$)
Wide multiples						
L1448 N ^b	A	03:25:36.53	30:45:21.35	...	N	8.24 ± 1.29
	B	03:25:36.34	30:45:14.94	7.3		2.15 ± 0.33
	C	03:25:35.53	30:45:34.20	16.3		2.95 ± 0.45
L1448 C	N	03:25:38.87	30:44:05.40	...	N	0.96 ± 0.16
	S	03:25:39.14	30:43:58.30	8.1		1.69 ± 0.27
NGC1333 IRAS7 ^b	PER18	03:29:11.26	31:18:31.08	...	Y	4.77 ± 0.73
	PER21	03:29:10.67	31:18:20.18	13.3		3.50 ± 0.54
	PER49	03:29:12.96	31:18:14.31	27.5		0.65 ± 0.10
NGC1333 IRAS4B ^e	B	03:29:12.01	31:13:08.10	...	Y	8.74 ± 1.36
	B'	03:29:12.83	31:13:06.90	10.6		0.02 ± 0.002
NGC1333 SVS13 ^b	A	03:29:03.75	31:16:03.76	...	Y	117.47 ± 18.19
	B	03:29:03.07	31:15:52.02	14.9		10.26 ± 1.57
	C	03:29:01.96	31:15:38.26	34.7		2.26 ± 0.35
NGC1333 IRAS2	A	03:28:55.57	31:14:37.22	...	Y	47.11 ± 7.22
	B	03:28:57.35	31:14:15.93	31.4		5.89 ± 0.91
B1-b ^b	S	03:33:21.30	31:07:27.40	...	N	0.35 ± 0.05
	N	03:33:21.20	31:07:44.20	17.4		0.17 ± 0.03
	W	03:33:20.30	31:07:21.29	13.9		0.12 ± 0.02
B1 P6+P10	Per6	03:33:14.40	31:07:10.88	...	N	0.21 ± 0.03
	Per10	03:33:16.45	31:06:52.49	31.9		0.47 ± 0.07
IC348MMS	Per11	03:43:57.06	32:03:04.60	...	N	2.34 ± 0.36
	E	03:43:57.73	32:03:10.10	10.2		0.10 ± 0.03
IC348SMM2	S	03:43:51.08	32:03:08.32	...	N	1.69 ± 0.27
	N	03:43:51.00	32:03:23.76	16.1		0.96 ± 0.16
IC348 P32+ED366	Per32	03:44:02.40	32:02:04.89	...	N	0.17 ± 0.03
	ED366	03:43:59.44	32:01:53.99	36.6		1.30 ± 0.21
Close binaries						
Per17		03:27:39.09	30:13:03.00	0.273	N	8.49 ± 1.31
L1455 FIR2		03:27:38.23	30:13:58.80	0.346	N	0.64 ± 0.10
NGC1333 IRAS4A ^e	A1 & A2	03:29:10.51	31:13:31.01	1.8	Y	10.17 ± 1.56
NGC1333 IRAS1 ^b	N & S	03:28:37.00	31:13:27.00	1.9	Y	11.00 ± 1.78
EDJ2009-156		03:28:51.11	31:18:15.41	3.192	Y	0.52 ± 0.08
IRAS 03282+3035 ^{b,c}		03:31:21.00	30:45:30.00	0.098	N	1.49 ± 0.23
IRAS 03292+3039		03:32:17.95	30:49:47.60	0.085	N	1.07 ± 0.27
B1-a		03:33:16.66	31:07:55.20	0.391	N	1.40 ± 0.23
Single systems						
L1455 IRS4		03:27:43.23	30:12:28.80	...	N	1.75 ± 0.27
L1455 IRS2 ^e		03:27:47.49	30:12:05.32	...	N	2.17 ± 0.35
L1455 Per25 ^b		03:26:37.46	30:15:28.01	...	N	1.09 ± 0.17
L1448IRS2		03:25:22.40	30:45:12.00	...	N	4.33 ± 0.67
L1448IRS2E		03:25:25.66	30:44:56.70	...	N	0.12 ± 0.02
NGC1333 IRAS5 ^b	PER52	03:28:39.72	31:17:31.89	...	Y	0.14 ± 0.02
NGC1333 IRAS5 ^b	PER63	03:28:43.28	31:17:32.90	...	Y	1.43 ± 0.22
RNO 15 FIR		03:29:04.05	31:14:46.61	...	Y	0.29 ± 0.05
NGC1333 SK1 ^b		03:29:00.52	31:12:00.68	...	Y	0.71 ± 0.11
NGC1333 IRAS6		03:29:01.57	31:20:20.69	...	Y	12.04 ± 1.86
NGC1333 IRAS4C ^e		03:29:13.52	31:13:58.01	...	Y	0.73 ± 0.11
B1-c		03:33:17.85	31:09:32.00	...	N	5.18 ± 0.80
HH211		03:43:56.80	32:00:50.21	0.3	N	1.61 ± 0.25

Notes. ^(a) N=No; Y=Yes. Clustered regions have 34 YSO pc⁻¹, while non-clustered regions have 6 YSO pc⁻¹, (Plunkett et al. 2013). ^(b) Systems from the sample in Murillo et al. (2018). ^(c) Reynolds et al. (2024) raise the possibility that IRAS 03282+3035 is not a close binary given recent observations, but cannot confirm. But given the results of the current work, there is no difference in classifying the system as a single or close binary in terms of physical parameters. ^(d) Possibly unresolved binary (Tobin et al. 2016). ^(e) No APEX HNC $J=4-3$ observations available. For NGC1333 IRAS4, JCMT HNC $J=4-3$ is available from Koumpia et al. (2016).

Table A.2. Sample of Starless cores

Region	Core	RA ^a	Dec ^a	Clustered? ^b	$L_{\text{bol}} (L_{\odot})^a$
IC348	SC16	03:44:01.0	32:01:54.8	Y	<1.6
IC348	SC17	03:43:57.9	32:04:01.5	Y	<2.0
IC348	SC18	03:44:03.0	32:02:24.3	Y	<0.6
IC348	SC21	03:44:02.3	32:02:48.5	Y	<1.2
L1455	SC40	03:27:39.9	30:12:09.8	N	<0.6
NGC1333	SC51 ^c	03:29:08.8	31:15:18.1	Y	<1.5
NGC1333	SC53	03:29:04.5	31:20:59.1	Y	<3.7
NGC1333	SC59	03:29:16.5	31:12:34.6	Y	<1.3
NGC1333	SC60	03:28:39.4	31:18:27.1	Y	<1.2

Notes. ^(a) Source coordinates and bolometric luminosities from Hatchell et al. (2007). ^(b) N=No; Y=Yes. Clustered regions have 34 YSO pc⁻¹, while non-clustered regions have 6 YSO pc⁻¹, (Plunkett et al. 2013). ^(c) Located at the edge of the small map centered on NGC1333 SVS13.

Table A.3. Molecular species in this work

Molecule	Transition	Frequency GHz	E _{up} K	log ₁₀ A _{ij}
HCN	J=1-0 F=1-1	88.63042	4.25	-4.62
	J=1-0 F=2-1	88.63185	4.25	-5.10
	J=1-0 F=1-0	88.63394	4.25	-5.10
HCO ⁺	1-0	89.18853	4.28	-4.38
HNC	1-0	90.66356	4.35	-4.57
N ₂ H ⁺	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=0-1	93.1716157	4.47156	-4.44039
	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=2-1	93.1719106	4.47158	-5.24996
	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=2-2	93.1719106	4.47158	-4.51356
	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=1-0	93.1720477	4.47158	-4.73371
	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=1-1	93.1720477	4.47158	-5.36331
	J=1-0,F1=1-1,F=1-2	93.1720477	4.47158	-4.87031
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=2-1	93.1734734	4.47165	-4.51355
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=2-2	93.1734734	4.47165	-5.24995
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=3-2	93.1737699	4.47166	-4.44038
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=1-0	93.173964	4.47167	-4.945
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=1-1	93.173964	4.47167	-4.6289
	J=1-0,F1=2-1,F=1-2	93.173964	4.47167	-5.8456
	J=1-0,F1=0-1,F=1-0	93.1762595	4.47178	-5.18949
J=1-0,F1=0-1,F=1-1	93.1762595	4.47178	-5.07339	
J=1-0,F1=0-1,F=1-2	93.1762595	4.47178	-4.67019	
C ¹⁸ O	1-0	109.78217	5.26	-7.20
¹³ CO	1-0	110.20135	5.29	-7.19
HNC	4-3	362.63030	43.51	-2.64

Notes. ^(a) Contains both ortho- and para forms.

References. All rest frequencies were taken from the Cologne Database for Molecular Spectroscopy (CDMS; Endres et al. 2016). Astronomically observed transitions of HCN are listed in Thorwirth et al. (2003). The HCO⁺ entry is based on Woods et al. (1975). The entries for HNC are based on Okabayashi & Tanimoto (1993). The ¹³CO entry is based on Klapper et al. (2000). The C¹⁸O entry is based on Winniewisser et al. (1985). The N₂H⁺ entry is based on Caselli et al. (1995); Pagani et al. (2009).

Table A.4. Gas Kinetic and Dust temperatures

Position	$I(\text{HCN})/I(\text{HNC}) J=1-0^a$	T_K^a K	T_{dust}^b K	T_{K,NH_3}^c K
L1448 C N	1.29 ± 0.13	15.0 ± 1.26	20.66 ± 0.6	...
L1448 C S	1.34 ± 0.13	15.0 ± 1.31	21.42 ± 0.65	...
L1448 N B	1.3 ± 0.08	15.0 ± 0.78	16.78 ± 0.43	...
L1448 N A	1.31 ± 0.07	15.0 ± 0.68	17.22 ± 0.48	...
L1448 N C	1.25 ± 0.07	15.0 ± 0.65	17.03 ± 0.35	...
L1448 IRS2	1.21 ± 0.18	15.0 ± 1.79	18.06 ± 0.34	...
L1448 IRS2E	1.15 ± 0.16	15.0 ± 1.61	12.42 ± 0.12	...
L1455 FIR2	1.12 ± 0.09	15.0 ± 0.92	14.61 ± 0.19	...
L1455 Per17	1.32 ± 0.08	15.0 ± 0.82	21.19 ± 0.62	...
L1455 IRS4	1.26 ± 0.08	15.0 ± 0.8	14.53 ± 0.24	...
L1455 Per25	1.25 ± 0.37	15.0 ± 3.68	16.17 ± 0.31	...
L1455 IRS2	1.13 ± 0.07	15.0 ± 0.75	14.02 ± 0.13	...
L1455 SC40	0.78 ± 0.07	15.0 ± 0.71	11.54 ± 0.1	...
NGC1333 SVS13C	1.18 ± 0.11	15.0 ± 1.09	18.51 ± 0.41	16.99 ± 0.21
NGC1333 SVS13B	1.2 ± 0.12	15.0 ± 1.16	20.79 ± 0.53	16.76 ± 0.19
NGC1333 SVS13A	1.18 ± 0.12	15.0 ± 1.23	23.03 ± 0.7	16.72 ± 0.22
NGC1333 IRAS2A	1.46 ± 0.2	15.0 ± 2.0	30.8 ± 1.53	17.12 ± 0.32
NGC1333 IRAS2B	1.45 ± 0.22	15.0 ± 2.16	18.59 ± 1.03	14.89 ± 0.36
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per18	1.18 ± 0.14	15.0 ± 1.36	19.03 ± 0.3	13.94 ± 0.21
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per21	1.62 ± 0.24	16.21 ± 2.42	18.99 ± 0.42	14.24 ± 0.34
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per49	1.56 ± 0.28	15.57 ± 2.78	14.74 ± 0.27	12.94 ± 0.32
NGC1333 IRAS4A	2.08 ± 0.17	20.78 ± 1.71	17.0 ± 0.39	15.56 ± 0.32
NGC1333 IRAS4C	1.39 ± 0.28	15.0 ± 2.85	14.67 ± 0.23	12.36 ± 0.21
NGC1333 IRAS4B	1.9 ± 0.21	19.03 ± 2.1	16.29 ± 0.36	13.3 ± 0.33
NGC1333 IRAS4B'	1.33 ± 0.17	15.0 ± 1.7	16.61 ± 0.43	12.46 ± 0.29
NGC1333 IRAS1	0.87 ± 0.23	15.0 ± 2.26	25.47 ± 0.9	14.39 ± 0.65
NGC1333 EDJ156	1.36 ± 0.21	15.0 ± 2.05	13.83 ± 0.14	15.2 ± 0.57
NGC1333 RNO15FIR	1.49 ± 0.15	15.0 ± 1.54	14.04 ± 0.13	14.89 ± 0.27
NGC1333 IRAS6	1.6 ± 0.19	15.97 ± 1.9	19.33 ± 0.35	16.11 ± 0.23
NGC1333 SK1	1.21 ± 0.17	15.0 ± 1.75	15.45 ± 0.18	12.23 ± 0.34
NGC1333 IRAS5 Per63	1.82 ± 0.53	18.2 ± 5.3	15.09 ± 0.14	10.18 ± 0.46
NGC1333 IRAS5 Per52	1.37 ± 0.21	15.0 ± 2.15	13.12 ± 0.12	11.77 ± 0.18
NGC1333 SC51	1.18 ± 0.1	15.0 ± 0.95	12.09 ± 0.05	12.4 ± 0.14
NGC1333 SC53	1.11 ± 0.18	15.0 ± 1.77	16.68 ± 0.12	14.64 ± 0.25
NGC1333 SC59	0.8 ± 0.18	15.0 ± 1.8	12.27 ± 0.05	11.71 ± 0.15
NGC1333 SC60	1.29 ± 0.24	15.0 ± 2.36	11.28 ± 0.08	10.93 ± 0.43
B1 bW	1.4 ± 0.19	15.0 ± 1.93	12.09 ± 0.12	...
B1 bN	1.36 ± 0.16	15.0 ± 1.59	11.9 ± 0.1	...
B1 bS	1.67 ± 0.22	16.7 ± 2.2	12.09 ± 0.12	...
B1 Per6	0.99 ± 0.24	15.0 ± 2.37	12.3 ± 0.07	...
B1 Per10	1.18 ± 0.33	15.0 ± 3.34	12.89 ± 0.11	...
B1 a	1.33 ± 0.19	15.0 ± 1.91	12.99 ± 0.08	...
IRAS 03292+3039	1.35 ± 0.4	15.0 ± 3.96	13.72 ± 0.21	...
IRAS 03282+3035	1.02 ± 0.14	15.0 ± 1.42	16.66 ± 0.42	...
B1 c	1.96 ± 0.28	19.61 ± 2.8	16.69 ± 0.37	...
IC348 SMM2N	1.48 ± 0.22	15.0 ± 2.25	15.19 ± 0.13	...
IC348 SMM2S	1.78 ± 0.33	17.81 ± 3.29	15.84 ± 0.13	...
IC348 MMSE	1.35 ± 0.29	15.0 ± 2.86	16.54 ± 0.23	...
IC348 Per11	1.46 ± 0.26	15.0 ± 2.65	16.83 ± 0.28	...
IC348 Per32	1.56 ± 0.24	15.65 ± 2.43	15.8 ± 0.11	...
IC348 ED366	1.32 ± 0.35	15.0 ± 3.47	17.93 ± 0.17	...
IC348 HH211	1.71 ± 0.34	17.09 ± 3.4	17.28 ± 0.35	...
IC348 SC16	1.25 ± 0.22	15.0 ± 2.23	16.31 ± 0.13	...
IC348 SC17	2.58 ± 0.69	25.79 ± 6.86	15.83 ± 0.09	...
IC348 SC18	1.76 ± 0.34	17.64 ± 3.39	15.23 ± 0.08	...
IC348 SC21	1.47 ± 0.37	15.0 ± 3.72	15.07 ± 0.05	...

Notes. ^(a) For ratios <1.5, the gas kinetic temperature is arbitrarily set to 15 K. See Section 5.2 for details. ^(b) Dust temperature obtained from the *Herschel* and *Planck* maps from Zari et al. (2016). ^(c) Gas kinetic temperature obtained from fitting NH₃ maps from Friesen et al. (2017).

Table A.5. Densities and Masses

Position	HNC $J=4-3/J=1-0$	$n(\text{H}_2)^a$ 10^6 cm^{-3}	$N(\text{N}_2\text{H}^+)^a$ 10^{13} cm^{-2}	$N(\text{HCO}^+)^a$ 10^{12} cm^{-2}	$M_{\text{gas}}(\text{N}_2\text{H}^+)^a$ $10^{-9} M_{\odot}$	$M_{\text{gas}}(\text{HCO}^+)^a$ $10^{-10} M_{\odot}$	M_{env} $M_{\odot}$
L1448 C N	0.9 ± 0.04	5.66 ± 4.02	2.37 ± 0.60	1.53 ± 0.18	10.90 ± 2.75	6.99 ± 0.82	3.11
L1448 C S	0.82 ± 0.03	5.16 ± 3.08	2.28 ± 0.21	1.47 ± 0.14	10.40 ± 0.95	6.74 ± 0.65	2.54
L1448 N B	0.21 ± 0.01	1.41 ± 0.75	3.47 ± 0.17	2.17 ± 0.21	15.90 ± 0.78	9.95 ± 0.97	7.33
L1448 N A	0.23 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.64	3.10 ± 0.13	1.92 ± 0.19	14.20 ± 0.60	8.80 ± 0.85	4.52
L1448 N C	0.2 ± 0.01	1.03 ± 0.62	2.53 ± 0.08	1.53 ± 0.15	11.60 ± 0.37	7.00 ± 0.71	4.05
L1448 IRS2	0.16 ± 0.01	0.82 ± 0.14	1.08 ± 0.02	0.66 ± 0.02	4.96 ± 0.07	3.01 ± 0.11	1.20
L1448 IRS2E	0.18 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.13	1.50 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.03	6.87 ± 0.05	4.17 ± 0.12	1.46
L1455 FIR2	0.47 ± 0.03	2.73 ± 1.72	0.55 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.05	2.74 ± 0.27	1.75 ± 0.23	0.42
L1455 Per17	0.33 ± 0.01	1.52 ± 0.84	1.09 ± 0.08	0.68 ± 0.08	5.36 ± 0.37	3.37 ± 0.39	0.45
L1455 IRS4	0.24 ± 0.01	1.21 ± 0.73	0.83 ± 0.05	0.51 ± 0.06	4.11 ± 0.24	2.53 ± 0.31	0.56
L1455 Per25	0.34 ± 0.06	1.68 ± 1.00	0.52 ± 0.05	0.33 ± 0.05	2.56 ± 0.23	1.62 ± 0.25	0.34
L1455 IRS2 ^b	...	1.79 ± 0.00	0.85 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.01	4.19 ± 0.04	2.71 ± 0.04	0.33
L1455 SC40 ^b	...	1.79 ± 0.00	0.95 ± 0.01	0.61 ± 0.01	4.68 ± 0.04	3.02 ± 0.04	0.56
NGC1333 SVS13C	0.17 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.59	3.29 ± 0.09	1.98 ± 0.20	16.20 ± 0.42	9.79 ± 0.96	2.73
NGC1333 SVS13B	0.31 ± 0.01	1.76 ± 1.03	2.34 ± 0.17	1.48 ± 0.17	11.60 ± 0.81	7.32 ± 0.85	3.41
NGC1333 SVS13A	0.49 ± 0.01	2.74 ± 1.77	1.90 ± 0.18	1.22 ± 0.15	9.38 ± 0.89	6.00 ± 0.75	1.42
NGC1333 IRAS2A	0.82 ± 0.03	5.23 ± 3.20	1.81 ± 0.20	1.17 ± 0.14	8.95 ± 0.96	5.77 ± 0.70	1.29
NGC1333 IRAS2B	0.28 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.69	0.89 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.07	4.40 ± 0.32	2.72 ± 0.37	0.41
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per18	0.23 ± 0.01	1.12 ± 0.61	1.79 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.10	8.82 ± 0.32	5.41 ± 0.52	1.40
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per21	0.38 ± 0.02	1.55 ± 0.84	1.39 ± 0.12	0.89 ± 0.13	6.88 ± 0.59	4.37 ± 0.62	1.57
NGC1333 IRAS7 Per49	0.13 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.46	0.75 ± 0.03	0.44 ± 0.05	3.70 ± 0.15	2.17 ± 0.24	1.08
NGC1333 IRAS4A	0.14 ± 0.01	0.56 ± 0.40	1.55 ± 0.09	0.89 ± 0.12	7.63 ± 0.43	4.37 ± 0.57	9.17
NGC1333 IRAS4C	0.15 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.46	1.38 ± 0.04	0.85 ± 0.07	6.81 ± 0.21	4.20 ± 0.35	1.43
NGC1333 IRAS4B	0.15 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.53	1.30 ± 0.09	0.79 ± 0.13	6.41 ± 0.44	3.89 ± 0.64	4.17
NGC1333 IRAS4B'	0.1 ± 0.01	0.60 ± 0.35	1.36 ± 0.07	0.78 ± 0.05	6.73 ± 0.35	3.85 ± 0.26	25.69
NGC1333 IRAS1	0.53 ± 0.03	2.21 ± 1.10	0.61 ± 0.06	0.39 ± 0.05	3.00 ± 0.28	1.92 ± 0.25	0.44
NGC1333 EDJ156	0.11 ± 0.02	0.66 ± 0.39	0.55 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.03	2.69 ± 0.09	1.56 ± 0.14	0.17
NGC1333 RNO15FIR	0.3 ± 0.01	1.63 ± 1.04	1.75 ± 0.15	1.09 ± 0.16	8.62 ± 0.74	5.39 ± 0.77	1.77
NGC1333 IRAS6	0.39 ± 0.01	1.59 ± 0.81	1.75 ± 0.12	1.11 ± 0.13	8.62 ± 0.59	5.49 ± 0.64	1.00
NGC1333 SK1	0.12 ± 0.01	0.80 ± 0.44	1.58 ± 0.04	0.94 ± 0.08	7.80 ± 0.21	4.64 ± 0.37	0.37
NGC1333 IRAS5 Per63	0.15 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.55	0.27 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.12	0.83 ± 0.16	0.11
NGC1333 IRAS5 Per52	0.24 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.66	1.10 ± 0.06	0.68 ± 0.08	5.44 ± 0.29	3.36 ± 0.41	1.00
NGC1333 SC51 ^b	...	1.44 ± 0.00	2.36 ± 0.02	1.50 ± 0.02	11.70 ± 0.08	7.42 ± 0.08	1.22
NGC1333 SC53 ^b	...	1.44 ± 0.00	1.02 ± 0.01	0.65 ± 0.01	5.05 ± 0.03	3.22 ± 0.05	0.81
NGC1333 SC59 ^b	...	1.44 ± 0.00	1.02 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.02	5.03 ± 0.10	3.19 ± 0.10	0.60
NGC1333 SC60 ^b	...	1.44 ± 0.00	1.30 ± 0.03	0.83 ± 0.03	6.41 ± 0.13	4.08 ± 0.14	0.62
B1 bW	0.16 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.56	1.85 ± 0.07	1.13 ± 0.12	9.23 ± 0.36	5.63 ± 0.60	4.48
B1 bN	0.13 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.47	1.85 ± 0.06	1.09 ± 0.10	9.23 ± 0.29	5.43 ± 0.49	6.12
B1 bS	0.18 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.58	1.53 ± 0.09	0.94 ± 0.13	7.65 ± 0.44	4.69 ± 0.66	5.08
B1 Per6	0.32 ± 0.03	1.68 ± 1.00	1.83 ± 0.14	1.15 ± 0.15	9.13 ± 0.71	5.76 ± 0.76	1.89
B1 Per10	0.31 ± 0.04	1.63 ± 0.95	1.66 ± 0.12	1.05 ± 0.14	8.30 ± 0.58	5.25 ± 0.68	1.77
B1 a	0.15 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.44	1.34 ± 0.04	0.82 ± 0.08	6.70 ± 0.22	4.09 ± 0.38	0.55
B1 IRAS 03292+3039	0.39 ± 0.02	2.32 ± 1.35	0.88 ± 0.10	0.56 ± 0.09	4.38 ± 0.52	2.81 ± 0.47	3.58
B1 IRAS 03282+3035	0.29 ± 0.02	1.51 ± 0.97	1.26 ± 0.08	0.79 ± 0.10	6.28 ± 0.38	3.93 ± 0.49	1.33
B1 c	0.55 ± 0.02	1.99 ± 1.23	1.75 ± 0.24	1.15 ± 0.22	8.75 ± 1.23	5.74 ± 1.12	2.10
IC348 SMM2N	0.27 ± 0.01	1.12 ± 0.56	0.80 ± 0.04	0.49 ± 0.05	3.82 ± 0.19	2.36 ± 0.25	0.78
IC348 SMM2S	0.23 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.63	0.45 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.05	2.16 ± 0.16	1.32 ± 0.23	0.55
IC348 MMSE	0.29 ± 0.01	1.63 ± 1.05	0.71 ± 0.07	0.45 ± 0.07	3.43 ± 0.34	2.15 ± 0.35	4.75
IC348 Per11	0.24 ± 0.01	1.20 ± 0.68	0.67 ± 0.05	0.41 ± 0.06	3.21 ± 0.22	1.99 ± 0.27	1.63
IC348 Per32	0.14 ± 0.01	0.74 ± 0.47	0.65 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.04	3.10 ± 0.12	1.83 ± 0.21	1.06
IC348 ED366	0.04 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.24	0.55 ± 0.12	0.25 ± 0.03	2.62 ± 0.56	1.19 ± 0.14	0.27
IC348 HH211	0.26 ± 0.02	1.20 ± 0.79	1.18 ± 0.10	0.73 ± 0.13	5.67 ± 0.47	3.52 ± 0.62	2.51
IC348 SC16 ^b	...	1.02 ± 0.00	0.89 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.01	4.27 ± 0.05	2.64 ± 0.07	0.51
IC348 SC17 ^b	...	1.02 ± 0.00	0.58 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.04	2.77 ± 0.17	1.83 ± 0.19	0.35
IC348 SC18 ^b	...	1.02 ± 0.00	0.32 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	1.53 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.05	0.59
IC348 SC21 ^b	...	1.02 ± 0.00	0.47 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	2.25 ± 0.03	1.40 ± 0.05	0.43

Notes. (a) Column densities, gas masses, and envelope dust masses calculated for circular regions of 18'' in diameter, approximately 5000 AU, centered on the sources listed in Tables A.1 and A.2. (b) Sources without HNC $J=4-3$ data, adopted $n(\text{H}_2)$ is an average of the corresponding region, which could be an upper or lower limit.

Fig. B.2. Integrated intensity maps of formyl cation HCO^+ 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to the signal-to-noise ratio indicated next to the panel title (i.e., 5σ or 3σ). Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.3. Integrated intensity maps of hydrogen isocyanide HNC 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to the signal-to-noise ratio indicated next to the panel title (i.e., 5σ or 3σ). Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.4. Integrated intensity maps of diazenylium N_2H^+ 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to the signal-to-noise ratio indicated next to the panel title (i.e., 5σ or 3σ). Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.5. Integrated intensity maps of carbon monoxide $C^{18}O$ 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to the signal-to-noise ratio indicated next to the panel title (i.e., 5σ or 3σ). Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.6. Integrated intensity maps of carbon monoxide ^{13}CO 1–0 toward five subregions in Perseus: NGC1333, L1448, L1455, B1, and IC348. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Maps are clipped to 5σ . Gas kinetic temperature map is overlaid in contours in steps of 10., 15., 20., 25., 30., 40. K. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.7. Kinetic temperature maps obtained from the HCN 1–0 / HNC 1–0 ratio for all observed subregions in Perseus. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Star symbols mark the locations of protostellar systems (Table A.1). Square symbols mark the location of starless cores (Table A.2). The circle symbol marks the position of L1448 IRS2E, whose nature is debated. Straight lines indicate outflow directions for the protostellar systems included in the MASSES survey (Stephens et al. 2017).

Fig. B.8. Intensity integrated maps of diazenylium N_2H^+ 1–0 (purple contours, see also Fig. B.2) overlaid on the kinetic temperature map (colorscale, same as Fig. B.7). Contours are in steps of 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, 14 and 16 $K km s^{-1}$. All maps are shown with the same colorscale range for comparison. Black filled circles are proportional to the derived H_2 density for each protostellar system. Derived densities were normalized to the largest value, found toward L1448 C. The normalized value was multiplied by an arbitrary value to make the filled circles visible on the map. The panel size does not influence the size of the filled circles.

Fig. C.1. Relations between envelope mass M_{env} and N_2H^+ gas mass ($M_{gas}(N_2H^+)$, *first row*, same as Fig. 3), and HCO^+ gas mass ($M_{gas}(HCO^+)$, *second row*). Bottom three rows show number of components versus gas mass ($M_{gas}(N_2H^+)$, *third row*; $M_{gas}(HCO^+)$, *fourth row*), and versus envelope mass (M_{env} , *fifth row*). The orange stars show multiple systems, the cyan diamonds show binary systems, and the gray circles show single protostellar systems. Each panel represents one of four ways of grouping the sample presented in this work, and their corresponding correlations. The lines and shaded areas show the linear regression for the data with the corresponding color. Solid lines indicate statistically significant correlations (Pearson r and Spearman ρ p -values < 0.05), while dashed lines show subsamples with p -values > 0.05 . See Section 5.5 for discussion on the figure.